

Chemistry of Thorium. Part IV. Interaction of Thorium(IV) Chloride and Some Phenols and Nitrophenols

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Preparation and properties of some addition and substitution compounds of ThCl_4 with phenols and nitrophenols have been studied and their structures discussed.

By the treatment of a boiling ammoniacal pyrocatechol solution with aqueous thorium nitrate, Rosenheim and Sorge¹ obtained a needle-shaped crystalline compound, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{Th}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{ONH}_4)_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Weinland and Sperr² prepared a pyridine pyrocatechol-thorium compound, $[\text{Th}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_4]\text{H}_4\text{Py}_2$. Rosenheim *et al.*³ prepared some complex pyrocatecholates of thorium with guanidine, pyridine, and NH_4^+ as cations. Olen Ryba *et al.*⁴ during calorimetric studies with rising pH values observed the formation of a blue complex of thorium with pyrocatecholate-violet. Funk and Rogler⁵ obtained $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot (\text{OPh})_2$ by heating anhydrous ThCl_4 with phenol directly or in benzene till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased.

It is evident that no systematic attempt has been made to study the action of ThCl_4 on phenols in non-aqueous media. The present communication deals with the study of the interaction of thorium (IV) chloride and some phenols and nitrophenols in ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous thorium (IV) chloride was prepared by the method of Dean and Chandler⁶ and extracted with dry ether. The chemicals used were of B. D. H. or E. Merck's "E.P." quality except *o*-cresol (May and Baker).

Method of Preparation

In all the cases, an excess of phenol in ether was mixed with an ethereal solution of ThCl_4 in a flask, fitted with drying tubes; the mixture was heated at 60° - 65° till the solvent vapourised away and subsequently the temperature was slowly raised to 10 - 15° above the melting point of the respective phenol and heating continued till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased. In cases with pyrocatechol, hydroquinone, and phloroglucinol, the

1. *Ber.*, 1920, 53B, 632.
2. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1925, 150, 69.
3. *Ibid.*, 1931, 196, 160.
4. *Chem. Listy*, 1957, 51, 1462.
5. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, 252, 323.
6. *Nuclear Sci. & Eng.*, 1957, 2, 57.

mixture was heated much below the melting point of the respective phenol to avoid decomposition of the products. The product was cooled, extracted with a suitable organic solvent, filtered, and washed free of the reactants. It was pressed between folds of filter papers, dried over fused CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator, and analysed.

In case of α - and β -naphthols, heating at $10\text{--}15^\circ$ above the melting points of the phenols provided mono-substitution products which on further heating at $60\text{--}70^\circ$ above the melting point of the respective naphthol yielded the di-substitution products.

Ethereal *ortho*- and *meta*- cresols on treatment with ThCl_4 solution in ether at the room temperature afforded only the addition compounds which, when heated with the excess of the respective cresol on a water bath, afforded crystalline substitution products.

Analysis.—Thorium was estimated as ThO_2 by charring a weighed quantity of the compound with H_2SO_4 (conc.), followed by oxidation of the organic matter with HNO_3 (conc.), and subsequently precipitating $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_4$ by an excess of NH_4OH . The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly, dried, ignited to ThO_2 , and weighed. Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method as AgCl .

General Properties.—It has been observed that the reaction with polyhydroxy-phenols is more rapid than that with monohydroxy phenols. The compounds are generally coloured, crystalline or semi-crystalline, insoluble in benzene, toluene, and CCl_4 but sparingly soluble in propanol, ethanol, and acetone. Addition products with cresols hydrolyse readily in open air and more rapidly on boiling with water or caustic alkali solutions; the rests are quite stable in open air, slowly hydrolyse in boiling water and caustic alkali solutions.

TABLE I

S.No.	Phenols used.	Colour of the product.	%Thorium.		%Chlorine.		Formula of the product.
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
1	α -Naphthol	Pinkish grey	47.63	48.10	21.89	22.11	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})$ $\downarrow$ -HCl(160.70°)
2	Do	Brownish black	38.90	39.40	12.69	12.05	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$
3	β Naphthol	Pinkish brown	47.59	48.19	21.73	22.11	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})$ $\downarrow$ -HCl (180.200°)
4	Do	Brownish black	38.84	39.40	12.53	12.05	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$
5	<i>o</i> -Cresol (in cold)	Pinkish brown	47.63	48.14	29.06	29.45	$\text{ThCl}_4(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3$ $\downarrow$ -HCl
6	Do (on heating at W.B.)	Pinkish white	51.76	52.09	23.48	23.89	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3)$
7	<i>m</i> -Cresol (in cold)	White	47.61	48.14	29.12	29.45	$\text{ThCl}_4(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3$ $\downarrow$ -HCl
8	Do (on heating at W.B.)	Dirty white	51.43	52.09	23.36	23.89	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3)$
9	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	Dirty brown	39.78	40.03	12.13	12.26	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{O})_2$
10	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Greyish white	39.84	40.08	12.40	12.36	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{O})_2$
11	Pyrocatechol	Grey	55.83	56.46	17.90	17.23	$\text{ThCl}_4(\text{O}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{C})$
12	Resorcinol	Brick-red	56.12	56.46	17.15	17.27	" "
13	Hydroquinone	Black	55.73	56.46	16.88	17.27	" "
14	Orcinol	Yellowish brown	54.10	54.60	16.38	16.70	$\text{ThCl}_2(\text{O}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\cdot\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{O})$
15	Phloroglucinol	Dark brown	53.21	54.34	16.38	16.62	$\text{ThCl}_4(\text{O}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\cdot(\text{OH})\cdot\text{O})$

Mono-substitution products with *o*- and *m*-cresols are hydrolysed more easily in comparison with the di-substitution products. Thus the stability of the products falls in the following order: addition product < mono-substitution < di-substitution.

DISCUSSION

An examination of the result shows that one molecule of ThCl_4 reacts with two molecules of a monohydroxy- (except *o*- and *m*-cresols) and one molecule of di- or tri-hydroxyphenol and two chlorine atoms of ThCl_4 are displaced, yielding di-substitution products, HCl gas being eliminated. With *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols, the reaction is similar to that with monohydroxy phenols, $-\text{NO}_2$ group remaining intact and only the OH group being affected.

Formation of addition products with *o*- and *m*-cresols, $\text{ThCl}_4(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$, in the cold is perhaps due to co-ordination which assumes covalent form on heating. The reaction may be represented as:

In trihydroxyphenol, only two OH groups are affected and it is not possible to ascertain the position of the unaffected OH group as the compound, when heated to a higher temperature, decomposes.

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